

**BIOECOLOGY OF MURIDAE FAMILY
REPRESENTATIVES****A.A. Jumabaeva**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17529381>**ARTICLE INFO**Received: 29th October 2025Accepted: 30th October 2025Online: 31st October 2025**KEYWORDS***Mice (Muridae) are the most complex family of rodents***ABSTRACT***The animal world, as an integral part of nature, plays a vital role in human life. Changes in the natural habitats of species cause significant changes not only in their distribution, numbers, and certain aspects of their ecology, but also in their importance.*

The animal world, as an integral part of nature, plays a vital role in human life. Changes in the natural habitats of species cause significant changes not only in their distribution, numbers, and certain aspects of their ecology, but also in their importance.

Mice (Muridae) are the most complex family of rodents. In a broad sense, it includes 15-17 subfamilies and about 280 genera, and in a narrow sense, about 120 genera. They are small to medium-sized. Body length ranges from 5 to 48 cm, tail is long (half or more of body length), often bare, covered with a scaly layer. In some tree-dwelling species, it is hairy with a small tuft at the tip.

Distributed in Africa, Eurasia (excluding polar regions), the Indo-Malayan region, New Guinea, Australia, and neighboring islands. A number of species are found alongside humans worldwide. In Russia, there are 5 genera: harvest mice (*Micromys*, 1 species), field mice (*Apodemus*, 3 species), wood mice (*Sylvaemus*, 5 species), house mice (*Mus*, 2 species); and rats (*Rattus*, 2 species).

Five representatives of the mouse family are found in Uzbekistan: the pygmy wood mouse (*Sylvaemus uralensis*), the house mouse (*Mus musculus*), the brown rat (*Rattus norvegicus*), the Turkestan rat (*Rattus turkestanicus*), and the short-tailed bandicoot rat (*Nesokia indica*).

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, only two species belonging to the mouse family are found: the house mouse and the short-tailed bandicoot rat.

The house mouse is a species that is active throughout the year, both synanthropically and in natural conditions, in all seasons in the Southern Aral region. It is widespread in cultivated fields, dense thickets along riverbanks, tamarisk groves, reed beds, saxaul forests, steep cliffs and slopes, and in residential areas of settlements. A house mouse is a small, long-tailed animal. The body length reaches 110 mm. Their diet is also diverse. In nature, they feed on seeds and grains, while in homes and household plots, they eat all kinds of food. Their burrow is very simple, with 2-3 entrances, and a depth of 25-30 cm. House mice are very

prolific and produce many offspring. Under favorable conditions for survival, they reproduce in homes throughout the year. Gestation lasts 20 days. Each birth produces up to 13-14 pups.

Found in the Amu Darya delta of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. In most cases, in the Amu Darya delta, we can also encounter the Transcaspian vole (*Microtus transcaspicus*) and the short-tailed bandicoot rat (*Nesokia indica* Gray) in areas where living conditions are almost identical.

The short-tailed bandicoot rat has a body length of 220 mm. It is often found along the shores of the Aral Sea, on the banks of irrigation canals, in dense reeds, in cultivated fields, in gardens, and in houses. Under favorable living conditions, short-tailed bandicoot rats reproduce year-round. They usually breed 2-3 times per season and give birth to an average of 6 pups. Gestation lasts 28 days. They are adapted to feeding on the underground parts of plants, namely the root system. Sometimes they also eat insects. They gnaw on the bark and roots of alfalfa, rice, wheat, barley, and large trees. They also readily consume various animal carcasses. Their burrow system is very complex. Several families settle in rows, digging burrows over a large area, causing significant difficulties in gathering grass and fodder in the pastures and using machinery. They pierce irrigation ditches. They pierce the walls of houses made of raw brick and clay, using them for burrows. They destroy orchards and white poplars that bear various fruits by eating their roots. Their activity begins as dusk falls.

The study of the bioecological characteristics of rodents (Rodentia) found in Uzbekistan, as well as in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, is of great importance. Especially in recent years, the transformational processes occurring as a result of changes in biotic and abiotic factors are manifested in the distribution of rodents and the occurrence of specific shifts in their ethology. Studying and comparatively analyzing such changes is of paramount importance.

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